

INVESTIGATING THE IMPACT OF INACCESSIBLE CIVIL STATUS AND PROPERTY DOCUMENTATION ON HUMAN RIGHTS AND RECOVERY IN CONFLICT ZONES: A CASE STUDY OF NORTHWEST SYRIA

ÇATIŞMA BÖLGELERİNDE ERİŞİLEMİYEN MEDENİ DURUM VE MÜLKİYET BELGELERİNİN İNSAN HAKLARI VE İYİLEŞME ÜZERİNDEKİ ETKİSİNİN İNCELENMESİ: KUZEYBATI SURIYE ÖRNEK OLAYI

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of inaccessible civil status documentation (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation on human rights and post-conflict recovery in conflict zones, focusing on Northwest Syria as a case study. The research highlights how the loss or inaccessibility of these essential documents severely undermines individuals' ability to access basic services, exercise their rights, and rebuild their lives after conflict. Without CSD, individuals lack legal identity, restricting their access to education, healthcare, humanitarian aid, and legal remedies. Similarly, the absence of HLP documentation exacerbates housing insecurity, property disputes, and forced displacement, impeding economic stability and post-conflict recovery.

Keywords: Civil Status Documentation (CSD), Human Rights, Post-Conflict Recovery, Northwest Syria, Conflict Zones

Öz

Bu çalışma, medeni durum belgelerine (CSD) ve konut, arazi ve mülkiyet (HLP) belgelerine erişimin olmamasının insan hakları ve çatışma sonrası toparlanma üzerindeki etkisini inceleyerek, Kuzeybatı Suriye'yi bir vaka çalışması olarak ele alıyor. Araştırma, bu temel belgelerin kaybı veya erişilemezliğinin bireylerin temel hizmetlere erişme, haklarını kullanma ve çatışma sonrasında hayatlarını yeniden inşa etme yeteneklerini ciddi şekilde nasıl zayıflattığını ortaya koyuyor. CSD olmadan bireyler, yasal kimlikten yoksun kalır ve bu durum, eğitim, sağlık hizmetleri, insani yardım ve yasal çözümlere erişimlerini sınırlar. Benzer şekilde, HLP belgelerinin yokluğu, barınma güvensizliğini, mülkiyet anlaşmazlıklarını ve zorla yerinden edilmeyi şiddetlendirerek ekonomik istikrarı ve çatışma sonrası toparlanmayı engeller.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Medeni Durum Belgeleri (CSD), İnsan Hakları, Çatışma Sonrası Toparlanma, Kuzeybatı Suriye, Çatışma Bölgeleri

EXTENDED ABSTRACT

Background:

The study adopts an inductive approach, analyzing quantitative data collected through a structured survey targeting internally displaced persons (IDPs), returnees, host communities, and Syrians living abroad. Findings reveal systemic barriers to documentation access, including financial constraints, bureaucratic

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inefficiencies, security concerns, and a lack of trust in documentation processes. These challenges perpetuate cycles of marginalization, poverty, and inequality, particularly affecting vulnerable populations such as women, displaced persons, and minorities. The research underscores the critical role of NGOs and civil society organizations in addressing documentation challenges through advocacy, legal aid services, and capacity-building initiatives. Additionally, the study highlights the urgent need for innovative interventions, such as mobile documentation units, digital registries, and community-based dispute resolution mechanisms, to restore access to documentation and promote equitable recovery. Moreover, this research contributes to a deeper understanding of the systemic challenges faced in conflict-affected regions. It provides actionable recommendations for policymakers, humanitarian organizations, and stakeholders to enhance documentation processes, strengthen governance systems, and support long-term recovery.

Research Purpose:

The research objectives aim to provide a comprehensive understanding of the impact of inaccessibility to civil status and property documentation on human rights and post-conflict recovery in conflict-affected areas, with a specific focus on Northwest Syria case. The study examines how the lack of access to these essential documents affects the population's ability to exercise their fundamental rights, secure basic services, and protect their housing and property rights. It identifies the overarching challenges that hinder access to civil status and Housing, Land, and Property (HLP) documentation in conflict settings and analyzes their broader socio-economic and legal consequences. On the other hand, the research explores the role of existing mechanisms and interventions designed to address these challenges, including legal aid programs, documentation support initiatives, and capacity-building efforts for relevant actors. Additionally, the study investigates the role of NGOs and CSOs in mitigating the documentation crisis, focusing on their contributions to legal support, advocacy, community awareness, and service delivery. Finally, the study aims to provide evidence-based recommendations for policymakers, international organizations, NGOs, and local actors to improve access to civil status and property documentation. These recommendations support justice processes, protect human rights, and contribute to sustainable post-conflict recovery and development.

Methodology:

The study adopts an inductive approach, beginning with the collection of primary data to identify patterns, barriers, and consequences that emerge from the experiences of affected populations. Through a structured quantitative survey, the research explores how the lack of documentation influences individuals' ability to access services, exercise their rights, and contributes to recovery efforts. By focusing on internally displaced persons (IDPs), returnees, and host communities, the study ensures diverse perspectives are captured. The design allows for the systematic collection and analysis of data to assess the challenges individuals face in obtaining documentation, the impact of these challenges on their rights and recovery, and the existing mechanisms aimed at addressing these barriers. The collected data is analyzed using both quantitative and qualitative methods. Closed-ended responses are statistically analyzed to identify patterns, trends, and significant challenges, ensuring reliability and precision in the findings. Open-ended responses are thematically analyzed to provide nuanced perspectives and contextual factors that enrich the quantitative results. This combination of methods enabled the study to address the research objectives comprehensively, exploring barriers to documentation access, assessing their human rights implications, and evaluating mechanisms to improve access.

Findings:

The findings in the case study shed light on Northwest Syria as an example of how prolonged conflict, displacement, and systemic marginalization can create a documentation crisis that severely impacts the ability of affected populations to access their basic rights and rebuild their lives. This case illustrates the compounded challenges faced by displaced communities, including IDPs, returnees, and marginalized groups such as ethnic and religious minorities, in securing civil status and property documentation amid insecurity, economic hardships, and institutional inefficiencies. The research findings underscore the profound impact of documentation inaccessibility on conflict-affected populations in the case that was in Northwest Syria (NWS), making it a unique case study. The crisis in NWS is marked by the convergence of internally displaced persons (IDPs), refugees, and marginalized groups, including ethnic and religious minorities into small and often isolated geographic areas. These communities, deprived of basic human

rights and essential civil status documentation (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) records, face significant barriers to rebuilding their lives. Without documentation, individuals are effectively denied recognition, preventing access to fundamental services such as education, healthcare, housing, and legal recourse. Security concerns further compound the issue, with many individuals expressing fear of traveling to registration centers located in conflict-affected or militarized areas fearing from being detained. The risk of violence, harassment, or detention at checkpoints deters many from seeking documentation. Additionally, the destruction of infrastructure, including the closure or inaccessibility of registration centers, exacerbates these challenges. For marginalized groups, such as ethnic and religious minorities, the risks are even greater, as they often face additional layers of discrimination and exclusion.

Conclusion:

The study provides actionable recommendations to address these challenges, including expanding legal aid, implementing mobile documentation units, and leveraging technology to streamline documentation processes. Strengthening governance, fostering partnerships between local and international stakeholders, and prioritizing vulnerable populations are essential steps toward resolving documentation issues and promoting recovery. By addressing these barriers, the region can move closer to ensuring human rights protection, fostering stability, and creating a foundation for sustainable development. This research contributes to the broader discourse on human rights and recovery in conflict zones, offering a nuanced understanding of the critical role documentation plays in shaping individual and collective outcomes. While the findings focus on Northwest Syria, they have implications for other conflict-affected regions, providing a framework for addressing similar challenges globally. Ultimately, addressing documentation inaccessibility is not just an administrative necessity but a moral imperative to uphold human dignity, ensure justice, and enable recovery in the aftermath of conflict.

1.INTRODUCTION

The issue of inaccessible legal civil status and property documents in conflict zones is a major concern that deserves attention. The loss and lack of Civil Status Documentation (CSD) and Housing Land Properties (HLP) documentation in conflict zone areas caused by the effects of hostilities, forced displacement, and shifting lines of control present major countrywide issues that have severe negative impacts on the lives, well-being, and claiming rights of individuals and communities. This research problem focuses on understanding the underlying causes and consequences of the inaccessibility, loss, and lack of CSD and HLP documentation in conflict zone areas by shedding light on Northwest Syria as a case study, with a particular emphasis on the inability to access official services due to safety concerns, financial barriers, and the challenges faced by individuals residing in areas outside government control.

Addressing this problem is essential for promoting human rights, social cohesion, and stability in the region. By scrutinizing the impact of inaccessible legal documents as a human rights violation on the social cohesion and demographic change on populations of the same country, the study aims to contribute to the discourse on the most pressing challenges and impacts on individuals where they can't claim their fundamental human rights in conflict zones. This can help identify areas for improvement, policy recommendations, and potential solutions to enhance access to civil status and property documentation for the population.

2.HUMAN RIGHTS

To fully comprehend the violation of human rights resulting from undocumented legal civil status and property records for individuals residing in a war zone, it is essential to possess comprehensive knowledge of the definition of rights and human rights in general.

Article 1 of the United Nations Human Rights Convention defines rights: "A right is an inherent entitlement held by all human beings, not granted by law. Human rights arise simply by being a human being." while defining human rights "Human rights are rights inherent to all human beings, whatever our nationality, place of residence, sex, national or ethnic origin, color, religion,

language, or any other status." (General Assembly resolution, 1966) This means that an individual does not have to earn or do anything in particular to be accorded these rights, and they are irrevocable and outside of the political sphere. They are 'inborn' even though some might come to be accepted by the public in order to exist within the legal framework. In the absence of a legal framework, legal civil status and property documents are not a requirement for an individual to exercise their right to be a human being, provided that they do not contribute directly to a human rights violation.

These rights are all interrelated, interdependent, and indivisible, while the improvement of one right facilitates the advancement of the others. They promote the equal dignity and worth of every person without discrimination of any kind. Human rights are neither privileges attained through the pain of others nor have a limited place or time. They have always been and are universal, all-inclusive, and inalienable. All people everywhere are entitled to them.

The availability of documents on civil status, house, and land property is not only a bureaucratic formality but also a basic human right and social justice that have to be respected. The denial or limitation of access to these important documents can have a strong impact, harming the rights of people to their identity, property, and justice. Civil status documents serve as the foundation for personal identity, containing vital information such as birth certificates, marriage certificates, and other records that establish an individual's presence within the legal framework of a community. The mentioned documents are not just administrative artifacts; they are important instruments that help people claim their rights, get the services they need, and become full participants in society. Nevertheless, when civil status documents are either inaccessible or inaccurately maintained, people are thus made to suffer the consequences and are prevented from going to school, getting healthcare, working, and getting legal recognition. The inaccessibility or inaccuracy of civil status documents can cause the state to lose the recognition of a person; hence, this condition happens to people with no citizenship, and they are likely to be exploited, trafficked, and discriminated against. Statelessness keeps people away from their basic human rights, for instance, the right to education, healthcare, and legal protection, and thus keeps them from leading a good life. Besides, people without civil status documentation may not be able to prove their familial relationships, get legal recognition for marriages or adoptions, or get inheritance rights; thus, they will be in a situation where they will be the victims of the abuse or otherwise be excluded (Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labor, 2024).

Also, house and land property documentation is of great importance in protecting people's property rights and, at the same time, giving people access to housing, land, and resources. For instance, property ownerships and mortgage agreements are the legal documents that serve as proof of ownership; they also mark the property boundaries and establish the rights and responsibilities that are related to the land and housing. House and land property documentation that is either inaccessible or not adequate can be the reason for the unfavorable consequences, which are mainly felt by marginalized communities and vulnerable people (IOM, 2018). The absence of documentation may lead to forced evictions, land grabs, and, hence, the displacement of individuals, which will deprive them of their homes, livelihoods, and cultural heritage. The insufficient documentation of land tenure also weakens land tenure security, thus, creating rounds of land wars, conflict, and insecurity. Besides, the property documentation that is not accessible worsens the inequalities since marginalized communities are the ones that are mostly affected by land-related injustices, which include land grabbing, deforestation, and environmental degradation (Cornerstone, 2021).

The paperwork that is not accessible or contested can also block economic development, thus, these economic problems will not be solved, and it will raise corruption and impunity as well. Besides, the denial or limitation of access to documents is a destructive act that leads to the unfair treatment of people in justice matters and continues the problem of injustice in the legal system. In the courts, the documentation that is proven to be correct is used as the most important evidence;

thus, people can claim their rights, stand up for the violations that have been committed, and still participate well in the court decision. Nevertheless, because documents can be unavailable or contested, the people will have problems seeking justice as they will not be able to produce the evidence that will support their claims or defend their rights. In this situation, people may be detained arbitrarily, denied due process, and other human rights violations are committed, hence, their marginalization and vulnerability are deepened. Besides, the refusal of documentation to the people can be the reason for sustaining the injustices systemically in the legal systems since the communities that are marginalized are the ones that are usually affected by the barriers to justice, for example, poverty, discrimination, and a lack of legal representation. The fact that documentation is unreachable also brings the rule of law to a nosedive; thus, public trust in the legal institutions is affected, and this, in turn, is followed by the violation of human rights (IOM, 2023).

Thus, access to complete and reliable documentation is a necessity for human rights, social justice promotion, and the creation of socio-economically equal societies. Civil status documents and house and land property documentation are the most important factors that prove the identity of people, secure their property rights, and give them the right to justice (Inter-Agency Standing Committee, 2015). Documentation that is inaccessible or contested is the reason why people are not being able to get to education, healthcare, housing, and legal recognition; thus, they are being disenfranchised. Thus, the accessibility, accuracy, and integrity of documentation are necessary for protecting human rights, development, and the creation of peaceful and inclusive societies.

The severe warfare in Syria has not only displaced millions of civilians but has also led to the general decay or demolition of the Civil Status Documents (CSDs). Running away from their houses while under airstrikes, bombings, and armed conflict, a lot of Syrians were forced to leave their belongings, among them, the essential identification documents. In the confusion of the migration aftermath, many of these documents are usually the ones that are lost, damaged, or left behind, causing the people to be stranded without identity or legal status. Without CSDs, Syrians in Northwest are the ones who must face all the difficulties in getting access to basic services like healthcare, education, and humanitarian assistance. The absence of these documents will make the people vanish from the view of the state and the international aid agencies, which in turn will increase their vulnerability, and at the same time, the efforts of assistance and protection will be impeded (Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labor, 2024).

The process of acquiring replacement CSDs in Northwest Syria is filled with bureaucratic obstacles, especially for the displaced people and those who are living in the places that are being disputed. The Syrian government's control over the issuance of CSDs, combined with the fragmentation of the administrative structures in the conflict-affected regions, are the main causes of the difficulties in obtaining new or replaced documents for the people who had lost their previous ones or had their documents damaged. Civilians in Syria who have been displaced usually face the difficulties of complicated regulations and administrative procedures. These difficulties may include long-distance travel to government offices or even negotiating with bribe-taking corrupt officials (IRC, 2016). The fact that the CSD services are not accessible makes the situation even worse for the people who are already the most vulnerable, such as women, children, and minorities, who are the ones that are very often affected by the bureaucratic obstacles and who have an even more difficult time proving their identity and accessing the necessary services (UNCHS, 1999).

The lack of CSDs thus subjects' people, especially women and minorities, to the increased danger of being discriminated against, exploited, and abused. Without a legal ID, a person may encounter difficulties in implementing his or her rights, like getting a job, a home, or legal protection. Women are the most vulnerable to exploitation, for example, forced marriage, trafficking, and sexual violence, since they do not have the documents that are the basis for the assertion of their legal status and the request for help. The same minorities, including ethnic and religious groups, for example, could be at risk of being discriminated against and excluded from services and opportunities as they are not able to produce CSDs. The absence of legal status not

only degrades people's dignity and freedom but also maintains poverty and marginalization circles, thus putting them at risk of exploitation and human rights breaches (NRC & UNHCR, 2021).

On the other hand, there have been a lot of cases of property confiscation in Syria, which often target members of a specific community or people who are seen as opponents of the regime. Armed groups, which are also government forces and non-state actors, are blamed for the actions of taking the land and homes of people, either for the sake of punishment or to prove their control over the strategic territories. The takeovers of private properties not only infringe on the people's right to own property but also cause the displacement of families from their homes, thus cutting them off from their sources of living. Besides, the ruining of property registries and land records makes it more difficult to prove property rights; thus, individuals are at risk of arbitrary seizing of their properties, and even after the conflict is over, the way back to their properties is not possible (NRC, 2024).

The ongoing fighting and insecurity in Syria have given rise to the phenomenon of displaced people, with millions of Syrians being made to leave their homes in search of safety. Yet, despite the fact that they will be forced to return, many become aware of the harsh reality of being evicted because their properties were occupied or confiscated by another person during their absence. It is extremely difficult to prove ownership without proper House, Land and Property (HLP) documentation, and, as a result, to reclaim their property, which usually remains an unsuccessful task. This breaks the people's right to own property, and at the same time, it puts to a stop any hope of the people and the community that they will build their new lives after the conflict (Cunial, 2011). Forced evictions are another way of causing displacement and, therefore, the continuation of the conflicts and instability in Syria (Justice for Life organization, 2020).

The chaos surrounding the HLP documentation in Syria has established a perfect condition for exploitation and abuse, wherein opportunistic individuals and groups are using it to get involved in unlawful transactions. The displaced families, in their desperate situation to get shelter and resources, may be forced or tricked into selling or giving away their properties at a small price, although it is less than the market value. Through the overall ineffectiveness of the legal system, the opportunists, which include the criminal networks and the unprincipled developers, will be able to get the properties that they are looking for through fraudulent means, so the legitimate owners will be disenfranchised and the tension within the communities will increase. The absence of transparency in the conflict of property and the inability of the one to hold the wrongdoer accountable sets the stage for the climate of freedom, where human rights abuses are not checked, and the victims are denied justice and restitution (OHCHR, 2015).

3.LITERATURE REVIEW

This section establishes the theoretical and conceptual foundation for understanding the inaccessibility of civil status documentation (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation in conflict zones, with a specific focus on Northwest Syria. The conceptual framework explains how these essential documents underpin fundamental human rights, access to justice, post-conflict recovery, and social cohesion. Analyzing the legal definitions, international human rights frameworks, and existing challenges associated with documentation, this framework provides a lens through which the study examines the systemic barriers, impacts, and potential solutions to address these violations. The subsequent sub-sections explore the key components of CSD and HLP documentation, their legal and administrative significance, and their role in safeguarding rights and promoting recovery in conflict-affected settings.

3.1.Definition of CSD and HLP -Civil Status and Property Documentation

Civil Status Document (CSD) and House and Land Property (HLP) Documentation are found to assume crucial roles in varying lawful, administrative, and authoritative procedures, and thus, serve as fundamental components in issues concerning individual distinguishing proof, marital status, and

the ownership of property. These records carry remarkable weight in both individual and collective settings, impacting the choices, privileges, and obligations of citizens within a specified jurisdiction. For individuals, having an extensive comprehension of CSD and HLP documentation is fundamental. CSDs, for example, encompass imperative individual data like name, date of birth, spot of birth, along with marital status. They act as essential evidence of character, identity, and civil status, vital for getting access to a variety of administrations and advantages, including yet not limited to passport and visa issuance, marriage enlistment, and social government assistance qualifications (Lagarde, 2010). Without precise and state-of-the-art CSDs, people might experience obstacles in different lawful exchanges and official strategies as well as procedures. So, it can be said that a civil status document is actually an authority record that gives data about a person's very own status within the legal system of a specific jurisdiction. This record commonly incorporates details like name, date of birth, spot of birth, marital status, and sometimes the details & information regarding the children. The Civil Status Document assumes an essential role in official procedures, government exchanges, and different regulatory processes. They act as verification of character, age, and civil status, and are frequently expected for activities, for example, applying for a visa, marriage enlistment, and to get certain social advantages (Zadravec, 2012).

On the other hand, HLP documentation relates to the proprietorship, limits, and legalities encompassing land properties, for example, houses and land parcels. These records act as the bedrock for laying out property freedoms, working with property moves, and guaranteeing consistency with drafting guidelines and tax collection regulations. Property contracts, titles, reviews, and home loan arrangements are among the critical parts of HLP documentation, each assuming a vital role in effectively defending property interests and settling conflicts (Ringelé & NRC, 2021). HLP documentation can be recognized as a source for enveloping a scope of authoritative records that lay out rights to proprietorship, limits, and other important data in regard to real estate properties, including houses, land divides, and related resources. These reports are fundamental for recording property exchanges, checking possession, and settling questions connected with property privileges (Inter-Agency Standing Committee, 2015). HLP documentation might incorporate titles, deeds, reviews, drafting authentications, contract arrangements, and local charge records, among others. Appropriately kept up with HLP documentation guarantees lucidity and straightforwardness in property exchanges, works with property move processes, and safeguards the interests of landowners and partners. As a result, having well-maintained HLP documentation is crucial for ensuring smooth and transparent property transactions.

Attorneys rely on these records to resolve disputes, safeguard clients' rights, and address legal matters involving identity or property. Similarly, administrative staff must ensure the accuracy and integrity of records during the processing of applications and maintenance of public archives. A comprehensive understanding of these documents is essential to navigate legal processes effectively and to uphold justice and accountability within society. CSD and HLP documentation serve as pillars of legal and administrative systems, intertwining individual identity, marital status, and property ownership rights. Their proper handling ensures not only the preservation of rights but also the smooth functioning of legal and governance structures (Cunial, 2011). Legal professionals and administrative personnel play a critical role in managing civil status documentation (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation.

3.2. International Human Rights Framework

The Syrian conflict has severely disrupted access to essential documentation, including civil status documents (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation. This widespread loss of paperwork has significantly impacted individuals, challenging fundamental principles of the International Human Rights Framework. The absence of these documents undermines individuals' ability to exercise their rights, access services, and secure basic protections, reflecting broader human rights violations.

The United Nations was established in 1945 as a global organization dedicated to promoting peace, justice, and human dignity. With 193 member states, the UN's founding principles emphasized the protection of fundamental human rights and the prevention of future conflicts. Building on this foundation, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) was adopted in 1948, becoming a landmark in the evolution of international human rights law. The UDHR represents a global commitment to safeguarding the sanctity and dignity of all individuals, regardless of nationality, race, or status. While it has been critiqued for being non-self-executing, the UDHR serves as a guiding framework for subsequent legally binding conventions and treaties, addressing a broad spectrum of civil, political, economic, social, and cultural rights. Together, the establishment of the UN and the adoption of the UDHR laid the groundwork for modern international human rights governance, inspiring efforts to address global challenges, including those arising from the Syrian conflict.

Article 15 of the UDHR guarantees the right to nationality, including the right to change one's nationality. Civil status documents, such as birth certificates, are critical for asserting nationality and accessing fundamental rights, including education, healthcare, and social security. In Northwest Syria, the absence of such documentation has left many individuals stateless, effectively invisible within legal and administrative systems. This statelessness exposes individuals to exploitation and denies them access to essential services (Rahman, 2022).

The International Covenant on Economic, Social, and Cultural Rights (ICESCR) further reinforces the importance of documentation through Article 11(1), which affirms the right of everyone to an adequate standard of living, including secure housing. HLP documentation serves as legal evidence of ownership, enabling individuals to claim and protect their property rights. Without such documentation, individuals face risks of eviction, loss of property, and compromised security, which undermine their survival and ability to rebuild their lives (Magdalena & Carmona, 2003).

The International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) complements these protections through Article 26, which prohibits discrimination based on race, sex, language, religion, or other status. The loss of CSDs and HLP documentation disproportionately affects marginalized groups, including women and minorities, who face additional barriers in accessing rights and services. Furthermore, Article 2(3)(a) of the Optional Protocol to the ICCPR ensures the right to effective remedies for covenant violations. However, the ongoing conflict and the absence of a functioning legal system in Syria prevent many individuals from seeking justice for the human rights violations stemming from documentation loss (Choudhury, 2002).

In the context of the Syrian conflict, the loss of CSDs and HLP documentation reflects a broader erosion of human rights. These documents are essential for accessing fundamental rights and protections, and their absence exacerbates the vulnerabilities of affected populations. The principles outlined in the UDHR, ICESCR, and ICCPR underscore the importance of restoring access to documentation as a critical step toward upholding human rights and fostering recovery in conflict-affected regions.

3.3.Civil Status and Property Documentations challenges

Civil status documentation faces numerous challenges that could come up in the conflicting regions. The chaos continues to be experienced, which blocks access to birth certificates, marriage registration, and death certificates. These personal documents become the soul of a family. Without them, many disputes would arise when an individual tries to access social services or whenever their legal rights are to be asserted. For example, in northwest Syria, where displacement is uncontrolled because of contention, families frequently lose their documentation in the midst of disarray and viciousness, leaving them without legitimate characters and helpless against exploitation and exclusion (ACAPS, 2023).

Another factor, a lack of housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation, further aggravates difficulties for the people of conflict zones. Transfer of residence, demolition of

properties, and land occupation without consent, among others, disorganize the ownership of land; hence, conflicts arise over land and accommodation rights. In northwestern Syria, for example, many previously displaced families go back to find their houses either occupied by others or ruined, which becomes a complicating factor in achieving property rights and rebuilding their lives that were completely destroyed. Missing in action are some land registries that are convincing and decent legal frameworks, which to a large extent contribute to the lack of restitution of properties while worsening the crisis of displacement (Cornerstone, 2021).

3.4. Impact of Inaccessibility CSD, HLP

The inaccessibility of civil status documentation and HLP rights significantly impacts individuals and communities in conflict-affected areas. This inaccessibility hinders their ability to claim legal rights, access basic services, and secure property ownership. Without proper documentation, individuals face barriers in obtaining justice, education, healthcare, and humanitarian aid, exacerbating their vulnerability and marginalization. Moreover, the lack of HLP rights undermines their economic stability and security, as they are unable to prove ownership or recover lost property, further perpetuating cycles of poverty and displacement. In purpose of the research objective, of the study, in the following section the researcher elaborates in regard of the impact of the CSD and HLP from different aspects.

3.5. Impact on Human Rights

The lack of CSD denies individuals legal identity, effectively rendering them invisible within administrative systems. Without birth certificates, marriage registrations, or death certificates, individuals face barriers in accessing critical rights such as healthcare, education, and social protections. The inability to prove marital or familial relationships can further complicate inheritance rights and leave individuals unprotected in legal disputes (Rahman, 2022). This lack of identity creates a cycle of marginalization, disproportionately affecting vulnerable populations such as women, children, and displaced individuals.

Similarly, the absence of HLP documentation erodes property rights, exposing individuals to the risks of eviction, land grabbing, and economic instability. These individuals cannot secure ownership, reclaim property, or defend against forced displacement. Without legal protection, property disputes often escalate, weakening trust in judicial systems and fostering grievances. As individuals are excluded from accessing legal remedies, impunity thrives, further undermining justice and perpetuating inequality (Jahn, 2015). Addressing these challenges is essential for safeguarding fundamental rights and fostering equitable governance.

This not only subverts their right to a secure home, yet also endangers their capacity to access the fundamental administrations attached to property ownership. Fundamentally, the shortfall of these documents causes a precarious situation where Syrians struggle to safeguard themselves and modify their lives (IOM, 2023).

3.6. Post-conflict Recovery and Development

The accessibility of civil status documentation (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation plays a critical role in post-conflict recovery and development. Ensuring access to these documents is essential for individuals and communities to rebuild their lives, secure their rights, and contribute to broader reconstruction efforts. Raising awareness about the right to identity through civil documentation is vital for making documentation systems innovative, cost-effective, and globally applicable to refugees, displaced populations, and low-resource communities. Reliable and accessible systems benefit all stakeholders by improving security, convenience, and affordability, enabling vulnerable populations to regain their legal and social footing in the aftermath of conflict.

The absence of CSD and HLP documentation creates substantial barriers to post-conflict recovery. Individuals without legal proof of identity or property ownership are excluded from participating in reconstruction processes, such as reclaiming properties, engaging in participatory governance, and accessing essential resources. This exclusion prevents affected populations from making meaningful contributions to the rebuilding of their communities, delaying normalcy, and obstructing economic growth. The inability to resolve property disputes, coupled with the lack of legal protections, undermines efforts to establish good governance, transparency, and accountability, further complicating recovery efforts (Global Protection Cluster & IOM, 2018).

In addition to slowing reconstruction, the inaccessibility of documentation exacerbates social and economic inequalities, hindering the development of inclusive governance systems. Without legal identity and property rights, individuals face systemic barriers that deepen poverty and foster marginalization. For example, the lack of secure property rights discourages investments and limits economic revitalization in conflict-affected regions. Addressing these issues requires innovative strategies and flexible legal frameworks tailored to the unique challenges of each affected community. Removing administrative, legal, and policy-related obstacles is critical for ensuring access to documentation and enabling sustainable development.

The reinforcement of property and land rights through inclusive and transparent processes is equally vital for promoting social cohesion. These efforts provide individuals with a sense of security and belonging, laying the foundation for sustainable peace and development. Strengthened property rights reduce conflicts, encourage economic investments, and rebuild trust in state institutions. Moreover, inclusive systems help prevent a relapse into violence and instability, fostering reconciliation and long-term stability (Lawry et al., 2016).

Conversely, the inaccessibility of documentation exacerbates social disorder and instability in conflict zones. Property disputes between neighbors, where multiple parties claim the same land, can fracture community relationships and disrupt social networks. The marginalization of undocumented individuals deepens inequalities and weakens trust in governance systems, further eroding social cohesion. Disrupted social ties make it challenging to foster peaceful relationships and rebuild communities, delaying the path to recovery. To address these challenges, effective systems for data protection and record preservation are essential for stabilizing post-conflict societies, enhancing reconciliation, and fostering social acceptance (Global Protection Cluster & IOM, 2018).

3.7.Existing Mechanisms and Best Practices

The Syrian conflict has exacerbated the documentation crisis, severely restricting the ability of affected populations to access their fundamental rights. In response, immediate measures and best practices have been developed to address violations of civil status documentation (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation. These mechanisms aim to mitigate the impact of lost or inaccessible documentation and provide pathways for affected individuals to regain their rights and protections.

One of the most effective mechanisms has been the deployment of mobile outreach teams by agencies such as UNHCR. These teams operate in conflict zones and refugee camps, facilitating the registration of births, marriages, and deaths. This approach accelerates the issuance of civil status documents, addressing immediate needs while reducing the risk of future barriers. Another innovative solution is the integration of voter databases with biometric identification systems, which ensures that displaced individuals can register their identity and rights regardless of location. Mutual recognition agreements between host nations and neighboring countries, spearheaded by UNHCR, further enhance the ability of Syrian refugees to access documentation, participate in local economies, and integrate into host communities (NRC & UNHCR, 2021).

For addressing the challenges related to HLP documentation, donor-supported rehabilitation of damaged land registries and the creation of digital backups have emerged as critical

interventions. These initiatives provide a secure repository for property records, reducing the risk of manipulation or loss and fostering trust in the documentation process. Additionally, alternative forms of dispute resolution, such as involving local mediators and arbitrators, have proven effective in resolving property rights abuses quickly and equitably. These mechanisms not only alleviate the burden on overburdened court systems but also empower communities to manage disputes independently.

Strengthening local authorities is another cornerstone of effective documentation management. Building the capacity of local governance structures ensures that displaced populations and other vulnerable groups can access documentation services without discrimination. Public awareness campaigns also play a pivotal role in educating communities about the importance of CSDs and HLP documentation. Such campaigns foster a culture of documentation security, encouraging individuals to safeguard their records and assert their rights.

To maximize the impact of these interventions, a collectively coordinated approach is essential. Agencies, donors, and local stakeholders must work together to implement sustainable mechanisms that address the documentation crisis. By integrating innovative solutions such as mobile outreach, digital registries, and community-based dispute resolution, these efforts can enhance the rights and protections of affected populations and contribute to long-term stability and recovery (Cornerstone, 2021).

3.8.NGOs and Civil Society Role to Address These Challenges

The complex challenges surrounding civil status documentation (CSD) and housing, land, and property (HLP) documentation in Syria necessitate a broad-based response, with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) and civil society playing a pivotal role in supporting affected communities. These entities use a variety of approaches to address the multifaceted issues associated with the documentation crisis, bridging gaps left by state and judicial institutions and ensuring the protection of fundamental human rights. One of the primary contributions of NGOs and civil society organizations is advocacy and awareness. Through global advocacy campaigns, these organizations highlight the Syrian documentation crisis, mobilizing international attention and support for policy changes that enhance access to necessary documents. Locally, NGOs conduct community workshops to educate individuals about the importance of documentation, the risks of losing records, and best practices for safeguarding essential documents. These efforts empower affected populations with the knowledge and tools to protect their legal rights (NRC & UNHCR, 2021).

In addition to advocacy, NGOs and civil society provide critical services such as legal aid and document recovery. They collaborate with organizations like UNHCR to deliver mobile services to remote and conflict-affected areas, facilitating birth registration, marriage documentation, and death certification. These services are particularly vital for displaced individuals and those in regions with limited access to government facilities. NGOs also assist with navigating bureaucratic barriers, offering legal advice to address disputes related to lost or disputed HLP documentation. Data collection and crisis evaluation are also integral to the work of civil society organizations. By gathering information on affected populations and vulnerable groups, NGOs identify risks, track interventions, and hold relevant authorities accountable for their responsibilities. This data-driven approach informs targeted strategies, enabling effective responses to documentation challenges.

Capacity building is another key focus of civil society efforts. NGOs mentor and train local organizations to establish sustainable, community-led initiatives that address documentation issues. These initiatives provide settlement services and empower communities to advocate for their rights, fostering resilience and self-reliance. Civil society also monitors and reports on the quality and accessibility of documentation recovery services, exposing non-compliance and delays to push for more efficient solutions (Justice for Life Organization, 2020).

NGOs and civil society are particularly valuable in areas where the rule of law is weak or inoperable. They act as a safety net, helping citizens navigate bureaucratic systems and advocating on their behalf when institutional responses are inadequate. By fostering a sense of solidarity and community, these organizations bridge the gap between individuals and state systems, addressing challenges that disproportionately affect marginalized populations such as women, children, and displaced persons.

Despite their critical contributions, NGOs and civil society face significant obstacles, including funding constraints, security challenges, and limited access to some regions. Overcoming these barriers requires coordinated efforts between NGOs, civil society, intergovernmental organizations, and local communities. By working together, these stakeholders can help Syrians reclaim their rights to legal identity, property ownership, and social protection, laying the foundation for long-term stability and recovery.

4.CONCLUSION

The issue of inaccessible civil status and housing, land, and property documentation in conflict zones represents a profound challenge to the protection of human rights and the facilitation of post-conflict recovery. As the reviewed literature demonstrates, the absence or loss of documentation hinders access to basic services, exacerbates vulnerabilities, and perpetuates cycles of marginalization, particularly for women, displaced persons, and minority groups. The systemic barriers to documentation, including financial, bureaucratic, and security-related obstacles, underscore the urgent need for comprehensive solutions that address both immediate needs and underlying structural issues.

Legal frameworks such as the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights and the Universal Declaration of Human Rights highlight the foundational role of documentation in safeguarding dignity and equality. However, enforcement remains a challenge in the absence of robust governance and trust in local systems. Practical interventions, such as mobile documentation units, digital registries, and community-based dispute resolution mechanisms, show promise but require scaling and integration with broader recovery efforts to maximize their impact.

The role of NGOs, civil society organizations, and international agencies is critical in bridging the gap between affected populations and their rights to documentation. Through advocacy, legal aid, and capacity-building, these actors can foster trust, empower communities, and support sustainable recovery. However, as the case of Northwest Syria and similar contexts illustrate, innovative approaches and coordinated efforts are essential to address the multidimensional impacts of documentation inaccessibility.

Moving forward, policymakers, humanitarian actors, and stakeholders must prioritize inclusive and transparent documentation processes, ensure the integration of housing and land rights into recovery planning, and strengthen mechanisms for accountability and governance. By doing so, the international community can uphold the rights of conflict-affected populations and support their efforts to rebuild lives, communities, and futures with dignity.

REFERENCES

- ACAPS (2023). Yemen: Challenges to Housing, Land, and Property Rights. ReliefWeb. Retrieved from https://www.acaps.org/fileadmin/Data_Product/Main_media/20230414_ACAPS_Yemen_challenges_to_housing_land_and_property_rights.pdf
- Bureau of Democracy, Human Rights and Labor. (2024). 2023 Country Reports on Human Rights Practices: Syria. United States Department of State. Retrieved from <https://www.state.gov/reports/2023-country-reports-on-human-rights-practices/syria/>
- Choudhury, T. (2002). The drafting of Article 26 of the International Covenant of Civil and Political Rights : part 1. ResearchGate. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/30052228_The_drafting_of_Article_26_of_the_International_Covenant_of_Civil_and_Political_Rights_part_1
- Cornerstone (2021). Housing, Land, and Property in Shelter Programs. Cornerstone OnDemand Foundation. Retrieved from https://ready.csod.com/clientimg/ready/emailUploads/Mobile_Guide/Mobile_Guide_HLP.pdf
- Cunial (2011). Housing, Land and Property: Training Guidance. NRC. <https://doi.org/978-82-7411-210-0>
- General Assembly Resolution (1966). International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. United Nations Human Rights. Retrieved from <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-civil-and-political-rights>
- Global Protection Cluster & IOM. (2018). Guidance Note Integrating Housing, Land and Property Issues into Key Humanitarian, Transitional and Development Planning Processes. International Organization for Migration (IOM). Retrieved from https://sheltercluster.s3.eu-central-1.amazonaws.com/public/docs/hlp-integration_guidance-note-2018_071918-final.pdf
- Inter-Agency Standing Committee (2015). Guidelines for Integrating Gender-Based Violence Interventions in Humanitarian Action: Reducing risk, promoting resilience and aiding recovery. Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC). Retrieved from <https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/working-group/iasc-guidelines-integrating-gender-based-violence-interventions-humanitarian-action-2015>
- IOM (2018). Integrating Housing, Land and Property Issues into Key Humanitarian, Transitional and Development Planning Processes. International Organization for Migration. Retrieved from https://sheltercluster.s3.eu-central-1.amazonaws.com/public/docs/hlp-integration_guidance-note-2018_071918-final.pdf
- IOM (2023). Housing Land And Property (Hlp): Overview Of Key Issues In Rural Sindh. International Organization For Migration. Retrieved from <https://pakistan.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1121/files/documents/2023-04/HLP%20Report-20%20Feb%202023-v5.pdf>
- IRC (2016). Identify Me: The Documentation Crisis in Northern Syria. International Rescue Committee. Retrieved from <https://www.rescue-uk.org/sites/default/files/document/1207/identify-me-july-2016-irc.pdf>
- Jahn, I. R. (2015). A Preliminary Assessment of Housing, Land and Property Right Issues Caused by the Current Displacement Crisis in Iraq1. Land Property and Reparations Division (LPR). Retrieved from https://www.iom.int/sites/g/files/tmzbd1486/files/our_work/DOE/LPR/A-Preliminary-Assessment-of-Housing-Land-and-Property-Right-Issues-Caused-by-the-Current-Displacement-Crisis-in-Iraq.pdf
- Justice for Life Organization (2020). Loss Of Evidentiary Documents In Syria Awaiting Fundamental Solutions. Justice for Life Organization. Retrieved from <https://jfl.ngo/wp-content/uploads/2020/04/Loss-of-Evidentiary-Documents-in-Syria-Final.pdf>

- Lagarde (2010). Recognition and registration of civil status documents in cross-border cases. Retrieved from <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/1339884/recognition-and-registration-of-civil-status-documents-in-cross-border-cases/1949918/>
- Lawry, Samii, Hall, Leopold, Hornby & Mtero (2016). The impact of land property rights interventions on investment and agricultural productivity in developing countries: a systematic review | 3ie. The International Initiative for Impact Evaluation (3ie). <https://doi.org/10.23846/SR14>
- Magdalena & Carmona (2003). The Nature of the Obligations Under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. The Nature of the Obligations Under the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights. Intersentia nv. Retrieved from https://books.google.com.tr/books/about/The_Nature_of_the_Obligations_Under_the.html?id=50wITYzNxnwC&redir_esc=y
- NRC (2024). Legal protection needs of refugees self-settled in secondary cities in Uganda. The Norwegian Refugee Council. Retrieved from <https://www.nrc.no/resources/reports/legal-protection-needs-of-refugees-self-settled-in-secondary-cities-in-uganda/>
- NRC & UNHCR (2021). Legal Identity and Housing, Land and Property Rights of Syrian Refugees from a Durable Solutions Perspective. Norwegian Refugee Council. Retrieved from <https://www.nrc.no/globalassets/pdf/reports/legal-identity-and-hlp-rights-of-syrian-refugees/legal-identity-and-hlp-rights-of-syrian-refugees-from-a-durable-solutions-perspective---english.pdf>
- OHCHR (2015). Land and Human Rights: Standards and Applications. OHCHR. Retrieved from https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/Publications/Land_HR-StandardsApplications.pdf
- Rahman, M. (2022). Universal Declaration of Human Rights. ResearchGate. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.35253.76005>
- Ringelé & NRC. (2021). Access To Housing, Land & Property In Forced Displacement Contexts. Nrc. Retrieved from <https://www.nrc.no/resources/reports/access-to-hlp-in-forced-displacement-contexts/>
- Syrian Documents (Civil and Identity Documents) (n.d.). Retrieved from <https://www.syrianationality.org/index.php?id=21>
- UNCHS (1999). Women's rights to land, housing and property in post-conflict situations and during reconstruction: A global overview. United Nations Centre for Human Settlements. Retrieved from https://www.globalprotectioncluster.org/sites/default/files/2023-04/Women%27s_Rights_to_Housing_Global_Overview_1999_EN.pdf
- Zadavec (2012). Civil status documents-challenges for civil registrars to circumvent problems stemming from the legal voidg. Retrieved from <https://policycommons.net/artifacts/1333680/civil-status-documents/1938369>
- Human Rights Watch (2023). Human Rights Watch's Role in Conflict and Crisis How HRW Documents Wartime Abuses, Advocates to Protect Civilians, and Promotes Justice. Retrieved from <https://www.hrw.org/news/2023/12/22/human-rights-watches-role-conflict-and-crisis>
- FRAME (2023). Human rights violations in conflict settings. Retrived from <https://repository.gchumanrights.org/items/35ab525e-cff9-4282-b6b6-71ba742f6f47>
- OHCHR (2023). International Legal Protection Of Human Rights In Armed Conflict. Retrived from https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/Documents/Publications/HR_in_armed_conflict.pdf